

AI-Assisted Therapeutic Insights from Patient-Literature Matched Digital Twins in Cancer

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Abstract

Motivation: Molecular tumor boards (MTBs) often must make important treatment decisions with limited information and time. These treatment decisions are critical for patient care and to help support this decision-making process, many cancer databases and tools have been created, synthesizing information available with respect to genes, mutations, drugs, and more. However, there have not been tools developed which focus on matching patients to literature, limiting the ability to efficiently access and use the wealth of published research.

Result: IDEATwin fills this gap, connecting patients to relevant biomedical literature in clear, defined ways that can be further analyzed to determine specific insights regarding the patient. By utilizing natural language processing, semantic search, and knowledge graph generation, IDEATwin integrates molecular profiling, clinical trials, and literature into a comprehensive network tailored to the patient. Network analysis of the knowledge graph highlights clusters, and using these clusters, context-informed generative summaries are able to synthesize information across different sources to yield useful points. This text-based framework enhances precision oncology by enabling MTBs to identify key relationships and accelerating the decision-making process critical to patient outcomes. These abilities of IDEATwin were demonstrated using a case study of EGFR-mutated small-cell lung carcinoma, and multiple avenues of improvement were hypothesized for future research.

Introduction

Spurred by the prevalence of biomarker testing and the application of deep learning techniques, precision medicine, particularly in the field of oncology, has made rapid advancements in the past few years¹. These advancements have been particularly useful in molecular tumor board (MTB) settings where results from biomarker testing are often used to determine the next best treatment². An MTB, usually composed of specialists in multiple fields such as clinical oncology, genomics, and pathology working together, is tasked with conducting and interpreting biomarker testing; identifying key genes and proteins; and finding relevant literature and clinical trials^{2,3}. Time is a critical resource in this comprehensive process, with some MTBs taking months to complete, during which patients are susceptible to further progression of their cancer. To address this need, many databases have been created to provide information such as cancer sequencing data⁴⁻⁶, existing treatment guidelines, and clinical trials that can be used to aid in decision making. However, these databases still require a great amount of time to find relevant data, creating a need for applications that can consolidate the data and provide a treatment approach quickly.

To accomplish this, the recent development of applications integrating clinical and multi-omics data from these databases has proven instrumental in providing personalized insights. However, while current applications aim to assist cancer clinical decision making by utilizing sequencing data, such as Platform for Oncogenomic Reporting and Interpretation (PORI), which analyzes and annotates patient sequencing data, they fail to connect patients with existing literature⁷. Other developments, like electronic clinical decision support tools (eCDSTs), use patient history to offer algorithmically-determined recommendations, but still lack incorporation of information published scientific literature^{7,8}.

To target these missing capabilities and provide a tool which utilizes the breadth of literature available on cancer, we propose the Information-Derived Enhanced Analytics Digital Twin (IDEATwin) application. IDEATwin leverages patient-specific information, publicly available cancer literature, and natural language processing methods to create patient-literature matched digital twins. The resulting digital twins can be leveraged to help MTBs and support treatment and diagnostic decisions, quickly find relevant existing research, and uncover key considerations that are traditionally difficult or time-consuming to address.

We expect IDEATwin to address many challenges currently faced by MTBs when surveying literature for insights that can be used to support treatment decisions. Foremost, the sheer volume and rapid growth of cancer-related literature makes it nearly impossible for MTBs to manually stay-up-to-date with all relevant research. IDEATwin will help address this issue, filtering to retrieve publications that share biomedical features with the patient and are determined to be relevant to the patient using similarity score calculations. A mechanism to narrow the breadth of literature needed to be considered is simple yet powerful, as it reduces computational resources

needed for analysis and helps mitigate loss of information when synthesizing information across many sources.

Furthermore, IDEATwin is unique in its ability to not only match literature to the patient but also incorporate clinical trials and other additional sources of information for patient-specific insights. IDEATwin introduces the novel concept of integrating multiple publicly available information sources into a unified textual framework. This framework allows for connections to be established between shared elements, enabling comprehensive analyses that go beyond any singular database or input. Not only is the patient matched to the literature, but the patient, literature, and clinical trials are all interconnected, creating a multidimensional network of relationships. By identifying and visualizing the shared elements across these sources, IDEATwin provides an unprecedented ability to uncover overlapping insights, enhance treatment personalization, and identify key gaps or opportunities for further exploration.

By employing a text-based methodology, IDEATwin can transform diverse cancer-related sources into a cohesive network that is personalized to the patient. By using natural language processing techniques, we can extract, normalize, and align biomedical entities, and then perform a variety of analyses. Ultimately, IDEATwin represents a significant step forward in precision oncology, empowering MTBs to leverage the full spectrum of available data efficiently and effectively while minimizing the risk of overlooking critical information.

Materials and Methods

IDEATwin is a tool for building a patient-specific treatment community network that was developed with Python and R, with future plans of integrating a web interface.

Data Sources

The basis of the digital twin comes from the patient's genomic profile and clinical note, establishing a knowledge base with information on the relevant genes, patient history, diagnoses made, past treatments, and more. Over 37 million publications were accessed from PubMed⁹, and clinical trials were accessed from ClinicalTrials.gov to match more information to the patient and grow the patient's knowledge base¹⁰.

Data Pre-Processing

The NCBI tool PubTator 3.0⁹ was used to annotate entities for the patient information, publications, and clinical trials based on the categories such as species, disease, variants, genes, chemicals, and cell lines. For IDEATwin, the categories of disease, genes, and chemicals are mainly focused on. The patient information and clinical trials were inputted as raw text and resulted in a JSON file with the extracted annotations for the entities. The publications had a direct API available for a JSON file to extract annotations. The JSON files were standardized to remove mentions of the species entity since the focus of IDEATwin is on humans and to remove repeated entities.

Using the extracted entities from the patient's genomic profile and clinical note, a feature paragraph was created. It consisted of every sentence with an entity and highlights them out of the large patient report. This feature paragraph was inputted into PubTator⁹ to identify the top n unique entity publication matches, where n is the desired number of publication matches.

The feature paragraph was encoded by MedCPT, a transformer model that retrieves relevant publications based on a query, to create vector embeddings¹¹. These vector embeddings were compared with the vector embeddings encoded by MedCPT for the PubTator publication matches by using a semantic search. Cosine similarity was used to determine the most similar publications to the patient's genomic profile and clinical note, represented by the feature paragraph.

The clinical trials used were identified in a case study IDEATwin was applied to.

Knowledge Graphs and Network Analysis

From the entities identified in the patient's genomic profile and clinical report, a knowledge graph was created to represent the starting knowledge base for the patient. The patient lies at the center of the graph, and unique entities are connected to it branching out. Each entity is colored based on category. The top n highest ranked publications were connected to the patient's knowledge graph, with the PMID being a new node connecting to the patient. Entities were also generated for each publication based on the categories of genes, chemicals, and diseases. Any existing entities were connected from its current occurrence in the patient's knowledge to the PMID, and new entities branch out of the PMID's node. Clinical trials were added in the same manner to the patient's knowledge graph increasing the complexity and number of relationships to the patient. Each NCT identifier was connected to the patient node, and entities were identified for each category. Any existing entities were also connected back to the patient and papers.

Building on the patient's knowledge graph from only the genomic profile and clinical note to include publication and clinical trial information establishes a large network connecting various resources. Network analysis was performed on this combined knowledge graph to determine prevalent clusters.

Generative Summaries

The prevalent clusters from the combined knowledge graph of the patient's genomic profile and clinical note, top publications, and relevant clinical trials, were used to create a generative summary by using a large language model. It provides quick insights into key relationships and entities for the patient.

Results

Overall Design of IDEATwin

IDEATwin uses cancer resources and the patient information to create knowledge graphs and generative summaries for quick and informative insights about the patient (**Figure 1**). Using the patient's genomic profile and clinical note, entities in relevant categories are annotated. The annotations are used to determine a feature paragraph to identify relevant publications for each category. The overall top matches are identified through a semantic search with vector embeddings. A knowledge graph for the patient is created from the entities in the patient report, top publications, and clinical trials. Generative summaries are created from the network analysis of the patient's knowledge graph.

Case Study: EGFR-mutated small-cell lung carcinoma

A published case study for EGFR-mutated small-cell lung carcinoma was used with IDEATwin¹². From the genes identified in the patient's tumor, the existing approach of using the main targetable genes was used to match about 70 clinical trials based on drug class and biomarkers. The case study identified another relevant clinical trial¹². By the time this clinical trial was identified, the patient had undergone 4 therapeutic strategies and 8 drugs in the span of 18 months since diagnosis. Compassionate use of the trial's inhibitors was offered since the patient was unable to travel to the site of the clinical trial, but the patient declined to undergo further treatment and is currently in hospice care. IDEATwin aims to accelerate this timeline of identifying potential treatments.

A knowledge base was first established using the patient's genomic profile and clinical note by creating a knowledge graph (**Figure 2**). There were 23 genes, 6 chemicals, and 3 diseases uniquely identified.

A semantic search was done to compare the top resulting publication for each entity from PubTator with the feature paragraph based on the patient report. In order to determine the highest-ranking publications overall, cosine similarity was measured (**Figure 3**). The top 50 publications were used to further develop the patient's knowledge base, and each publication's entities were identified and added to the knowledge graph (**Figure 4**).

The 70 clinical trials identified in the existing approach were added to the knowledge graph to make it more complex and information-rich for the patient (**Figure 5**). Network analysis was performed on the combined patient, publication, and clinical trials graph to identify key clusters (**Figure 6**). The modularity score was 0.54, representing moderate strength in the clusters.

A generative summary was created for the circled cluster, including information from the patient genomic profile and clinical note, publications, and clinical trials. It provided quick insights for the key clinical trials related to the patient and makes a way to summarize within and across networks.

Discussion

The IDEATwin framework represents a significant step forward in leveraging artificial intelligence and natural language processing methods to bridge the gap between molecular profiling and actionable clinical insights. By combining knowledge contained in biomedical literature, clinical trials, molecular profile reports, and clinical notes specific to the patient, IDEATwin enables oncologists to efficiently synthesize information and supports more-informed treatment decisions. This approach not only saves time but also enhances the specificity of treatment decisions to the patient of interest, which is critical in the rapidly evolving field of precision oncology.

The key strength of IDEATwin lies in its ability to not only identify biomedical attributes relevant to the patient across diverse data sources, but also to connect between these attributes. These connections, clearly visible in the patient knowledge graph created, help understand in what ways different sources of information relate to each other. However, in this aspect, there are many future enhancements that can be made to improve usefulness in clinical decision making. Implementation of relationship extraction between biomedical entities would allow for better analysis of the existing data, as characterizing the specific ways in which entities are connected would greatly improve clustering, generative summary creation, and other downstream processing.

The downstream analysis of the knowledge graph generated by IDEATwin also offers multiple opportunities for further development. As a primary step, various statistical analyses can be run on the various nodes, edges, and clusters contained in the knowledge graph to determine highly influential nodes in the knowledge graph network, representing biomedical attributes or sources of information that are most critical.

In addition to statistical measures, the generative summary function of IDEATwin can be enhanced. Currently limited to analyzing network nodes and edges within a cluster, the LLM-generated summary, while context-informed, is limited in its scope. By expanding to take inputs both within and between clusters, the generative summaries have the potential to be much more insightful, drawing connections across various patient attributes. Combining these enhancements will provide much more information to clinicians, MTBs, and other stakeholders in the treatment decision making process.

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Figures

Figure 1. Overview of IDEATwin's design. Workflow diagram of IDEATwin, showing the process from having only the patient information to creating knowledge graphs and generative summaries.

Figure 2. Knowledge graph created from EGFR-mutated small-cell lung carcinoma patient's genomic profile and clinical note. The patient is the center node, and entities branch out around it. Green nodes represent genes, purple nodes represent chemicals, and red nodes represent diseases.

Figure 3. Ordered plot representing the semantic search results for the most similar publications. The red dot represents the feature paragraph, and each blue dot represents a publication. The highest score possible is 1.0, showing an exact match with the feature paragraph.

Figure 4. Expanded knowledge graph with top 50 publications and patient information. The connections between a shared entity from the publications and the patient are highlighted.

Figure 5. Complexity increased knowledge graph with 70 clinical trials, top 50 publications, and patient information. The increased density of the nodes is apparent in the center, with other entities branching out.

Figure 6. Graph after knowledge graph with clusters identified. The colors represent different clusters, and the colors are recycled. The size of a cluster's node represents the number of connections to it. The circled cluster was used to create the generative summary due to the diverse set of resources connecting to it.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

